

Task Based Learning Approach

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Annotation: This paper includes some information about usage of TBLT approach and discusses some advantages and disadvantages of using this approach while teaching second language. Moreover, the information about how students can be engaged by employing this method is mentioned as a recommendation.

Key words: motivation, approach, target language, first language, practice, activity, task.

The type of teaching method used in language learning is very important. A student can understand language concepts more effectively if the teaching method is suitable for them. Task Based Learning Approach is one of the widely used methods used in second language learning. Willis (1996) states that this method is derived from the communicative language teaching method.

In addition to this idea, Brown (1994: 83) indicates, "Task-based learning is not a new method. Rather, it simply puts the tasks at the center of its methodological focus. He considers the learning process as a set of communicative tasks that are directly related to the educational goals they serve and whose goals go beyond language practice.

Since the 1980s, the task-based approach has been increasingly used in the field of foreign language teaching. A task-based approach aims to provide opportunities for students to acquire language both orally and in writing through learning activities designed to engage students in natural, practical, and functional use of language for meaningful purposes.

Before giving a broad definition of the task-based educational approach, we have to talk about what the task is and how its place is manifested in the task-based educational method.

Task

A task is an activity in which the target language is used by the learner for a communicative purpose to achieve an outcome" (Willis, 1996).

A task is a classroom activity that engages students in understanding, producing, or interacting with the target language, where the focus is on meaning rather than form. (Noonan, 2004)

Task-based language teaching method

Task-based language learning (TBLT) is an approach that allows students to actively communicate in order to achieve a goal or complete a task. The TBLT method focuses on developing students' communicative language skills by using language to solve a task and then solve it.

In task-based language teaching, the main focus is not on the grammar of the language, but on how the student can use the language, how to solve the task, and for this reason, this direction is considered a practice-based direction. From the selection of the task to the assessment process, all thought is focused on the outcome, i.e. how the student uses the language, to what extent the given task affects the student's ability to use the language they are learning, whether the main participant in the learning process is the student or the teacher.

Task-based language teaching puts the learner at the center of the learning process and allows them to understand that language is a tool for solving real problems. Task-based language learning itself teaches important skills. Students learn how to ask questions, how to discuss a given question, how to interact in groups, and how to work. In-group tasks, they can observe different approaches to problem solving, and at the same time learn how others think and make decisions.

TBL includes following steps:

Pre-task

Initially, the teacher introduces the topic and gives clear guidelines on upcoming stages. Here, employing lead in questions can be asked in order to check students background knowledge. Moreover, teacher's explanations can be effective by showing some examples from previous students' tasks.

Task

The main stage where students start working on their tasks in groups or pairs. The teacher plays role of a monitor and offer suggestions or hints if it is needed. However, it should be mentioned that the teacher controls if students use their first language or target language. Obviously, students have to use target language.

Post-task

Having completed the task last stage starts. In this stage, students can review their works. Peer observations can be also effective way of giving feedback. This stage offers students the chance to reflect on their work and analyze it in order to make better results in future.

Advantages and disadvantages

TBLT can be suggested as a valid approach however, TBLT is also has revealing weakness. Number of scientists give examples as:

- there is no opportunity to work on grammar rules thoroughly and vocabulary features as well;
- instead of L2 L1 is mostly used;
- planning is time consumed;
- lazy and low level students can not be motivated;
- everything is controlled by the teacher;
- not all the students can be engaged or motivated.

Nevertheless,

- TBLT can be used for all ages;
- students feel free to use vocabulary or grammar according to their understanding as here, everyone pays attention the meaning not the form;
- it allows meaningful communication;
- students can discover their target language by communication or through conversation.

In conclusion, task based approach can be an effective way of using language. Sitting in a classroom for hours and being lectured by teacher is not suitable way for acquiring, learning or producing languages. Every students needs to be engaged and motivated to participate. Moreover, while taking part in various activities and solving problems by using even minor language elements can make students motivated. TBLT can help students not only learn that very language but it creates a friendly atmosphere among students teams.

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